

A Study on the Comprehension of Behavioral Programming Variants Supplementary Material

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APPENDIX

The following appendix presents the results per question of the controlled experiment conducted as part of the paper *A Study on the Comprehension of Behavioral Programming Variants*. Note on Analysis: While we use Mann-Whitney tests for statistical inference of Likert data, we report means and standard deviations in tables for readability. This follows common practice in software engineering research while ensuring appropriate statistical analysis.

Table 1 presents results for ISE students in the comprehension task. The BP group outperformed the COBP group in most areas, answering more questions correctly on execution semantics and alignment across topics. In Q4 and Q7, the difference in alignment correctness was significant, and the effect size was small to medium for Q4 and medium for Q7. Additionally, the BP group was more confident, and the difference was statistically significant in most cases (effect size was small to medium). However, COBP students performed better in identifying code alignment for blocking internal or single events (Q2 and Q3) and answering the execution semantics question related to complex in-place event overrides (Q5). Nonetheless, this difference was not statistically significant. When examining time, we found that the BP group was faster in about half of the cases, while the COBP group was faster in the other half.

Table 2 presents the results for SE students in the comprehension task. The BP group surpassed the COBP group on execution semantics questions in about half of the cases (without statistical significance). In guarding questions (Q4 and Q7), the dif-

ference in alignment correctness favored BP and was statistically significant, with an effect size leaning towards medium. Conversely, the COBP group solved its questionnaire in less time than the BP group in most cases. Also, the COBP students answered the execution semantics correctly (in questions Q3, Q5, and Q6) at least as well, if not better than the BP students. Furthermore, COBP students performed better at identifying code alignment (in questions Q1, Q5, and Q6). The b-threads of Q5 and Q6 in BP include a part that identifies the current context and a part that defines what action should be taken based on this context. In contrast, the COBP b-threads contain only action specifications. Nevertheless, the differences for the COBP group were not statistically significant.

Table 3 presents the ISE students' identification task results. The BP group showed a statistically significant advantage in correctness for enhancement-related questions (Q1–Q3), with a medium effect size, and for guarding a simple event (Q6), with a small effect size. For guard and blocking questions (Q4–Q5), BP performed better but without statistical significance. In the complex event override (Q7), COBP had a non-significant advantage. As seen in Q5 and Q6 of the comprehension task, BP's b-threads combine context identification and actions, while COBP's focus solely on actions, favoring COBP in such cases. BP participants were significantly more confident, with small-to-medium effect sizes. COBP generally completed tasks faster, though differences were not statistically significant.

Table 4 portrays the results of the SE students for the identification task. Similar to the ISE students, the BP group had an advantage in correctness in the enhancement-related questions (Q1–Q3). For questions Q2–Q3, this difference was statistically significant with a small-to-medium effect size. The BP group showed an advantage in guard-blocking related

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Table 1: Results per question — ISE — Comprehension task*

Question	Concept	Bug	DV	BP	COBP	Sig (M-H)	Effect (r)
Q1	Encapsulation	No	Execution correctness	0.83 (0.38)	0.59 (0.50)	0.051	0.250
			Alignment correctness	0.79 (0.41)	0.65 (0.48)	0.235	0.152
			Confidence	3.17 (0.87)	2.97 (0.80)	0.308	0.131
			Time	6.89 (4.95)	4.48 (2.42)	0.013	0.316
Q2	Guard — Block Internal Event	Yes	Execution correctness	0.42 (0.50)	0.27 (0.45)	0.238	0.151
			Alignment correctness	0.63 (0.49)	0.76 (0.43)	0.274	0.140
			Confidence	3.38 (1.06)	3.05 (1.20)	0.392	0.110
			Time	3.68 (2.33)	4.97 (3.44)	0.147	0.186
Q3	Guard — Block Single Event	Yes	Execution correctness	0.83 (0.38)	0.65 (0.48)	0.119	0.200
			Alignment correctness	0.46 (0.51)	0.51 (0.51)	0.676	0.053
			Confidence	3.75 (0.85)	2.97 (0.87)	0.001	0.432
			Time	3.06 (1.30)	4.54 (2.85)	0.035	0.270
Q4	Guard — Block Multiple Events	No	Execution correctness	0.92 (0.28)	0.89 (0.31)	0.753	0.040
			Alignment correctness	0.96 (0.20)	0.65 (0.48)	0.005	0.357
			Confidence	3.96 (0.75)	3.05 (1.05)	0.001	0.416
			Time	2.33 (1.31)	2.61 (1.48)	0.269	0.142
Q5	Guard — Override Event	No	Execution correctness	0.67 (0.48)	0.70 (0.46)	0.768	0.038
			Alignment correctness	0.58 (0.50)	0.46 (0.51)	0.348	0.120
			Confidence	3.00 (1.14)	2.32 (0.97)	0.014	0.316
			Time	5.58 (2.64)	4.83 (2.37)	0.332	0.124
Q6	Enhancement	No	Execution correctness	0.75 (0.44)	0.73 (0.45)	0.862	0.022
			Alignment correctness	0.71 (0.46)	0.70 (0.46)	0.963	0.006
			Confidence	3.88 (0.85)	3.19 (1.08)	0.012	0.320
			Time	2.73 (1.75)	2.96 (1.60)	0.370	0.115
Q7	Enhancement with Guard	Yes	Execution correctness	0.79 (0.41)	0.70 (0.46)	0.444	0.098
			Alignment correctness	0.83 (0.38)	0.30 (0.46)	0.000	0.519
			Confidence	3.83 (0.70)	3.03 (0.80)	0.000	0.500
			Time	3.93 (2.21)	2.92 (1.88)	0.063	0.238

*Execution and alignment correctness are measured on a scale of 0-1. Confidence is on a five-point Likert scale, and time is measured in minutes.

questions (Q4–Q5), although the difference was not statistically significant. In Q6, which covers guarding and overriding a simple event, the BP group again had an advantage (not statistically significant). Consistent with the ISE group, the COBP group has an advantage in Q7. This again suggests that a b-thread that only deals with “what to do” in the current context, is more clear to the developer (though this difference was not statistically significant). In terms of confidence, the BP group was more confident in most answers. Regarding time, the COBP group performed faster on most questions, though these differences were generally not statistically significant.

Table 2: Results per question — SE — Comprehension task

Question	Concept	Bug	DV	BP	COBP	Sig (M-H)	Effect (r)
Q1	Encapsulation	No	Execution correctness	0.84 (0.37)	0.79 (0.41)	0.674	0.061
			Alignment correctness	0.84 (0.37)	0.90 (0.31)	0.581	0.080
			Confidence	3.42 (1.07)	3.55 (0.99)	0.718	0.052
			Time	6.23 (2.94)	4.02 (2.62)	0.001	0.475
Q2	Guard — Block Internal Event	Yes	Execution correctness	0.74 (0.45)	0.59 (0.50)	0.291	0.152
			Alignment correctness	0.89 (0.32)	0.79 (0.41)	0.361	0.132
			Confidence	3.89 (0.88)	3.90 (0.86)	0.964	0.007
			Time	4.02 (2.47)	3.29 (1.96)	0.222	0.176
Q3	Guard — Block Single Event	No	Execution correctness	0.84 (0.37)	0.93 (0.26)	0.329	0.141
			Alignment correctness	0.58 (0.51)	0.41 (0.50)	0.268	0.160
			Confidence	3.68 (0.82)	3.66 (0.86)	0.902	0.018
			Time	3.74 (1.64)	3.98 (2.20)	0.848	0.028
Q4	Guard — Block Multiple Events	No	Execution correctness	0.89 (0.32)	0.86 (0.35)	0.741	0.048
			Alignment correctness	0.89 (0.32)	0.62 (0.49)	0.039	0.298
			Confidence	4.00 (0.67)	3.69 (0.76)	0.184	0.192
			Time	3.68 (1.58)	3.55 (2.50)	0.559	0.084
Q5	Guard — Override Event	Yes	Execution correctness	0.79 (0.42)	0.79 (0.41)	0.976	0.004
			Alignment correctness	0.63 (0.50)	0.76 (0.44)	0.349	0.135
			Confidence	3.47 (0.96)	3.07 (1.10)	0.262	0.162
			Time	6.23 (2.63)	5.40 (2.57)	0.175	0.196
Q6	Enhancement	Yes	Execution correctness	0.89 (0.32)	0.97 (0.19)	0.327	0.141
			Alignment correctness	0.68 (0.48)	0.79 (0.41)	0.399	0.122
			Confidence	3.47 (0.90)	3.62 (0.62)	0.766	0.043
			Time	2.54 (1.07)	2.88 (2.12)	0.781	0.040
Q7	Enhancement with Guard	No	Execution correctness	0.79 (0.42)	0.76 (0.44)	0.806	0.036
			Alignment correctness	0.89 (0.32)	0.48 (0.51)	0.004	0.417
			Confidence	3.58 (1.07)	3.59 (0.82)	0.912	0.016
			Time	3.23 (1.44)	3.07 (1.62)	0.632	0.069

*Execution and alignment correctness are measured on a scale of 0-1. Confidence is on a five-point Likert scale, and time is measured in minutes.

Table 3: Results per question — ISE — Identification task

Question	Concept	DV	BP	COBP	Sig (M-H)	Effect (r)
Q1	Enhancement	Correctness	0.88 (0.34)	0.27 (0.45)	0.000	0.586
		Confidence	4.00 (0.59)	3.14 (1.06)	0.001	0.438
		Time	2.79 (1.55)	2.84 (1.54)	0.858	0.023
Q2	Enhancement — Block Multiple Events	Correctness	0.96 (0.20)	0.65 (0.48)	0.005	0.357
		Confidence	4.13 (0.61)	3.46 (1.10)	0.015	0.312
		Time	2.39 (1.11)	1.96 (1.10)	0.421	0.103
Q3	Enhancement — Wait and Block Multiple Events	Correctness	0.88 (0.34)	0.41 (0.50)	0.000	0.463
		Confidence	3.75 (0.99)	3.14 (1.00)	0.018	0.302
		Time	2.04 (1.04)	2.14 (1.21)	0.994	0.001
Q4	Guard — Block Single Event	Correctness	0.96 (0.20)	0.92 (0.28)	0.547	0.077
		Confidence	4.25 (0.74)	3.38 (1.11)	0.001	0.409
		Time	1.77 (0.81)	1.49 (0.71)	0.126	0.196
Q5	Guard — Block Multiple Events	Correctness	0.63 (0.49)	0.57 (0.50)	0.659	0.057
		Confidence	3.13 (0.95)	3.24 (0.95)	0.681	0.053
		Time	3.60 (1.84)	2.18 (1.71)	0.001	0.431
Q6	Guard — Override Event	Correctness	0.92 (0.28)	0.70 (0.46)	0.048	0.253
		Confidence	4.04 (0.91)	3.24 (1.01)	0.002	0.394
		Time	1.98 (1.18)	1.45 (0.74)	0.074	0.229
Q7	Guard — Complex Override Event	Correctness	0.46 (0.51)	0.70 (0.46)	0.058	0.242
		Confidence	2.92 (0.97)	3.14 (0.82)	0.515	0.083
		Time	2.68 (1.20)	1.83 (1.09)	0.010	0.328

*Correctness is measured on a scale of 0-1. Confidence is on a five-point Likert scale, and time is measured in minutes.

Table 4: Results per question — SE — Identification task

Question	Concept	DV	BP	COBP	Sig (M-H)	Effect (r)
Q1	Enhancement	Correctness	0.95 (0.23)	0.72 (0.45)	0.055	0.277
		Confidence	4.26 (0.81)	4.10 (0.72)	0.347	0.136
		Time	2.47 (1.12)	3.17 (2.38)	0.499	0.098
Q2	Enhancement — Block Multiple Events	Correctness	1.00 (0.00)	0.66 (0.48)	0.004	0.411
		Confidence	4.11 (0.81)	3.86 (0.52)	0.224	0.175
		Time	2.54 (1.39)	2.40(1.72)	0.652	0.065
Q3	Enhancement — Wait and Block Multiple Events	Correctness	0.95 (0.23)	0.66 (0.48)	0.020	0.336
		Confidence	4.11 (1.05)	3.31 (0.66)	0.001	0.476
		Time	2.33 (1.51)	1.78 (1.32)	0.208	0.182
Q4	Guard — Block Single Event	Correctness	1.00 (0.00)	0.93 (0.26)	0.247	0.167
		Confidence	4.42 (0.96)	3.90 (0.82)	0.014	0.353
		Time	1.37 (0.61)	1.07 (0.75)	0.118	0.226
Q5	Guard — Block Multiple Events	Correctness	0.84 (0.37)	0.69 (0.47)	0.238	0.170
		Confidence	3.63 (1.21)	3.79 (0.68)	0.946	0.010
		Time	4.23 (1.90)	1.84 (0.86)	0.000	0.681
Q6	Guard — Override Event	Correctness	0.95 (0.23)	0.79 (0.41)	0.143	0.212
		Confidence	4.16 (1.01)	3.97 (0.87)	0.297	0.150
		Time	2.02 (1.05)	1.66 (0.63)	0.712	0.053
Q7	Guard — Complex Override Event	Correctness	0.63 (0.50)	0.72 (0.45)	0.503	0.097
		Confidence	3.32 (1.20)	3.28 (0.88)	0.732	0.049
		Time	2.42 (1.12)	1.88 (0.89)	0.069	0.262

*Correctness is measured on a scale of 0-1. Confidence is on a five-point Likert scale, and time is measured in minutes.